

DEVELOPMENT OF WOMEN'S SPORTS IN NAVOI REGION

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In the last decade of the 20th century, judo among girls became somewhat popular in Navoi region, as in many other regions of the republic. On March 12-15, 1996, the republican championship in judo among girls born in 1981-1983 was held in Samarkand. In these competitions, Jamila Shamilova took 3rd place in the girls' weight category up to 33 kilograms, Lyudmila Kozhemyakina took 1st place in the girls' weight category up to 36 kilograms, Olga Kuldosheva took 4th place, Maria Kozhemyakina took 5th place in the girls' weight category up to 45 kilograms, Elena Cherginskaya took 4th place in the girls' weight category up to 51 kilograms, Olga Balakirova, Nastya Malikhina took 5th-6th places, and Oksana Korenko took 3rd place in the girls' weight category up to 57 kilograms. In 1997, the "Guli" women's football team participated in the Republican Championship and took 4th place in the competition. This year, the "Guli" football team took 2nd place in the Cup of the Republic of Uzbekistan held in Bukhara. Following these achievements, 4 female players from the team were invited to the national team. In order to popularize women's football, women aged 14 to 20 began to be recruited to football clubs.

In the early years of independence, table tennis among women's sports brought the name of Navoi region to the world stage. Manzura Inoyatova, an unrivaled athlete in table tennis, first gained unique experience by participating in the Asian Junior Championship held in India in 1997. In 1998, at the World Junior Games in Moscow (Russia), Manzura Inoyatova, together with Saida Burkhanhodjaeva, won a bronze medal in tennis. In 1999, the talented tennis player Manzura Inoyatova was named the winner of the World Games in Stockholm (Sweden) and the European Open Cup in Germany, taking the top step of the podium. Thanks to Manzura Inoyatova, who became the world champion among youth in table tennis, a tennis court was built in the center of Khatirchi district. The installation of a modern court and benches for referees and spectators gave impetus to the further development of tennis in the district. It is noteworthy that in the judo competitions held in the Navoi region, at first, girls of other ethnicities than the local Uzbeks participated more, but by 2000, the proportion of local representatives had increased significantly. In 2000, the republican championship among girls in judo was held in Tashkent on June 22-

25. In these competitions, K. Koldosheva took 3rd place in the girls' competition up to 35 kilograms, S. Atamurodova took 3rd place in the girls' competition up to 38 kilograms, N. Kanatboeva took 3rd place in the girls' competition up to 44 kilograms, R. Bekmurodova took 3rd place in the girls' competition up to 48 kilograms, and in the girls' competition up to 63 kilograms L. Kojemyakina took the 1st place, and E. Mogilina took the 3rd place in the women's competition weighing more than 63 kilograms.

In order to continue the legacy left by our ancestors, which leads to mental and physical perfection, in connection with the "Year of Women", the Republican Festival "Tomaris Games" was held in Jizzakh region in 1999, and in Shakhrisabz city in 2001. On April 18-20, 2002, a regional tournament was organized in kurash among girls and boys for the prize of the "For a Healthy Generation" Foundation, in which athletes from all districts and cities participated. Although Tashkent city did not lose the first place in the Uzbekistan Rhythmic Gymnastics Championship held on May 15-18, 2001, the Navoi region team rose one step higher and took second place, which indicates the development of rhythmic gymnastics in the region. In the team competition, Bukhara region took 1st place, while Navoi region was considered worthy of 2nd place. The team of Yulduz Umarova, Yulia Norova, Marina Denisova, Nadya Shishkina, and Ksenia Marchenko, coached by Irina Butko and Albina Pavlova, scored 20.6 points, narrowly beating Bukhara region (20.7 points).

It is noteworthy that despite the participation of famous representatives of rhythmic gymnastics Galeka Gulyaeva, Lena Podgornova, Tanya Yarkina, Regina Volitsina, Ira Panina in these competitions, Navoi athletes proved that they are not inferior to others in terms of talent. In individual competitions, the podium of the competition was taken by Navoi Nastya Berestetskaya, while 5th and 6th places were taken by representatives of the Navoi region team Yulia Strelkina and Rimma Khodzakhmedova. The continuous development of rhythmic gymnastics led to the formation of a unique school in the Navoi region. The foundation of the Navoi gymnastics school was laid by skilled masters of sports Z. Levshina, V. Shevchenko, S. Smirlova. E. Zhukova, A. Pavlova, I. Butko, K. Bekbulatova, N. Berestetskaya and other famous athletes who trained at this rhythmic gymnastics school have repeatedly conquered the arenas of Uzbekistan and the world.

In competitions organized on a republican and regional scale, women's teams from all regions, including Navoi region, participated and gained extensive experience in competitions in rhythmic gymnastics, athletics,

swimming, volleyball, basketball and other sports. From May 25 to June 2, 2002, 16 team competitions were held in the women's basketball sport of the Universiade competitions among higher educational institutions in Bukhara. Although the women's teams of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute and Navoi State Mining Institute took 7th place in these competitions, basketball players such as Elena Borisova, Svetlana Ukraintsova, Albina Saidova, Gulzhayna Shodieva, Elena Cherkasova, Alexandra Lapshina gained experience by competing with strong opponents and skilled athletes.

Such competitions organized on a republican scale served to develop the talents and abilities of Navoi athletes. In particular, Gulbahor Shodiyeva, a representative of the Navoi regional chess team, became the champion of Uzbekistan among 12-year-olds, while Dinora Aleksandrova, a follower of world champion Manzura Inoyatova, took 3rd place in the "Umid nihollari" sports competitions held in Fergana in 2003. In 2003, which was full of successes, the "Navoi OZIBO'SM (Olympic reserve specialized children and youth sports school)" volleyball team was organized at the initiative of the Navoi regional Department of Culture and Sports under the head coach of Victoria Tagaeva.

This team has achieved high results this year. In particular, the "Navoi OZIBO'SM" volleyball sports club took 2nd place in the 2003 Uzbekistan Championship and 2nd place in the 2004 Uzbekistan Cup. 10 members of the women's team who successfully played in the Higher League games became candidates for masters of sports, while Ksenia Vasilieva and Elbina Narbekova received the title of masters of sports of the 1st category. They successfully participated in the Higher League games of the Navoi region in basketball and volleyball, taking 2nd place among the 3rd round of the Higher League women's teams. The construction of modern sports complexes in all regions of our country, including gyms, tennis courts, swimming pools, and fitness centers, and the start of work of female coaches in them, served as an important factor in the popularization of sports among girls. By 2005, 40 percent of girls in urban areas of our republic and 35.7 percent in rural areas were involved in sports. This indicator indicates that women's sports are developing rapidly in all regions of our country.

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